

CHARACTERISTICS, SIGNS AND THEIR ANALYSIS OF FORMATION OF STUDENTS' LINGUISTIC AND LANGUAGE COMPONENTS THROUGH ADJECTIVE WORD GROUPS IN PRIMARY CLASS MOTHER TONGUE LESSONS

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Abstract. *As a result of research carried out in this article, attention is paid to the characteristics and signs of students' formation of linguistic and linguistic components in terms of quality vocabulary in elementary mother tongue classes. Also, a short analysis of them was shown.*

Keywords: *Quality vocabulary, linguistic competence, linguistic outlook, cognitive culture, language units, lexical and grammatical consistency.*

In today's globalization process, modernizing and rapidly developing social life, fundamental reform of the education system remains the need of the hour. In addition to being able to effectively use innovative pedagogical technologies in education, it is noted that the development of students' knowledge, skills, and abilities in science is insufficient.

Currently, it is envisaged that education will be organized on the basis of a competency-based approach, based on this, we will briefly consider the meaning of the word competency as follows.

The word "competence" comes from the word "to compete" and means "to compete", "to compete", "to compete". Literally translated, it means "ability to compete". According to the scientific pedagogical and psychological sources, competence and competence are very complex, multi-part concepts that are common to many disciplines. Therefore, its interpretations are different both in size and content, and in terms of meaning and logical content.

The essence of the term is also described on the basis of concepts such as "efficiency", "adaptability", "achievement", "success", "comprehensibility", "effectiveness", "readability", "quality", "quantity". Accordingly, we accept educational competencies according to the definition given in the approved standard.

In today's educational environment, competence is demanded by students in every subject. The science of mother tongue and reading literacy, which is taught in general education schools of our republic, accepts such a demand.

Taking into account the role of the mother tongue in the formation of the student's personality and general culture, it is appropriate to consider the formation of linguistic competence as a means of expanding the students' linguistic worldview and their knowledge of the language as a unique semiotics. This is an important condition for the formation of system and social phenomena and linguistic and communicative competences. The formation of linguistic competence is inextricably linked with the problem of comprehensive development of the student, his cognitive culture and, in this regard, the development function of school grammar.

It should be emphasized that it is important to determine the characteristics of students' language and linguistic competence formation in the process of learning the formation of linguistic competences in terms of quality vocabulary in primary school mother tongue classes.

In order to determine the level of linguistic competence, it is also appropriate to give tasks to young students in order to determine how they understand the place and purpose of language units in speech, and what linguistic features they rely on when qualifying language units. It is very important for young students to be able to answer the questions of why qualitative aspects serve in the structure of words, phrases and sentences, and how they differ from each other.

At the initial stage of formation of linguistic competence, it is also important to use methods and technologies that serve to develop the idea of a sentence as a minimal communicative unit and play a key role in the minds of students. Because the linguistic competence of students of this age is supported by speech practice. In the future, this role will fade into the background. The main purpose of the adjective sentences that young students have seen and learned is to use them in creating a text. Such an idea gradually strengthens in connection with the formation of students' not only linguistic, but also communicative competence. At the same time, the achievements of students in the direction of formation of linguistic competence in the following academic years also attract attention. It is gratifying that more than half of the students of the junior school describe the sentence, demonstrate a clear understanding of the role of speech in communication, and rely on the very large features of a certain language unit.

In order to determine the characteristics of the formation of linguistic competence in terms of adjective vocabulary in the primary grade mother tongue classes, offering several tasks of the language to young students is also effective in this process. Character that showed the ability of students to find the grammatical basis of the sentence, to establish grammatical and semantic connections in its composition (choice of phrases); the ability to distinguish a sentence from a set of adjective words and phrases, the ability to determine the boundaries of sentences related to the adjective word group in the text; If it serves to determine the ability to syntactically correct the sentence on the given topic and to use the words and concepts, phrases related to the quality of words, it will be an excellent light on light.

Also, it is important not to forget that the system of studying the quality category in primary grades aims to consistently enrich and complicate the learning material from the lexical and grammatical aspects. Students learn the lexical and grammatical meanings of adjectives and adjectives from the period of literacy training up to the 4th grade in the scope of the primary-grade native language program. In the period of literacy training, the meaning of the words indicated by the teacher, "How does an apple taste? What is the color of an apple? What is the size of an apple?" they learn practically by observing based on questions like.

In primary-grade native language classes, students' speech is enriched with new adjectives, the meaning of adjectives known to them in advance is clarified. Adjectives serve to enrich students' speech and imagination. Adjectives allow to clearly describe and express things and events. Using this opportunity, teaching to compose a creative text will clarify students' thoughts and increase the effectiveness of their speech.

The use of color pictures is also very effective in teaching quality. The picture affects the students' intuition, reveals aspects of it that they have not yet encountered in their life experience, and helps them to understand familiar phenomena.

For example, drawing a colorful picture of nature to the students' attention and creating several quality compounds based on one word as a result of giving assignments shows the level of the students' vocabulary (Appendix 1). Given tasks like the ones in the app, students create a set of adjectives based on the pictures shown. For example,

Based on task 1, students can create the following sets of adjectives. Colors: white, blue, blue, brown, yellow, yellow, red, black, green;

Based on task 2: Clear sky, cloudy sky, blue sky, clear sky, dark cloudy sky, white cloudy sky, calm sky;

Task 3: High mountain, snowy mountain, arched mountain, rocky mountain, snowless mountain, peaked mountain;

Task 4: Wild bear, brown bear, ugly bear, white bear, harmless bear, clown bear and finally;

Based on task 5: Pleasant wind, cold wind, strong wind, soft wind, warm wind, morning wind, evening wind, mountain wind.

"Adjective - word group" is explained based on the combinations made by the students. After that, it will be appropriate to move on to the formation of linguistic competences related to adjectives. It should also be mentioned that in the process of studying adjectives and word groups in general, the main goal is to enrich the student's vocabulary and to develop the ability to use words practically in speech. With this goal in mind, it is not unreasonable to emphasize the formation of linguistic competences in primary school mother tongue classes.

Linguistic analysis is not paid enough attention in elementary school mother tongue textbooks. In the 1st-2nd grade mother tongue textbook, there are no assignments to provide theoretical information about any type of linguistic analysis, to develop practical skills. In the 3rd grade textbook, when studying "Word composition", it is taught to show the composition of the word, what parts it consists of using conditional lines.

It is known that the term "grammatical analysis" is used in school practice. In our opinion, the term "grammatical analysis" is specific only to morphological and syntactic phenomena. "Linguistic analysis" includes other parts of linguistics. From this point of view, we found it necessary to use the term "linguistic analysis».

REFERENCES

1. Dilshoda Jalilova Ural qizi. BO‘LAJAK BOSHLANG‘ICH SINIF O‘QITUVCHILARIDA AXBOROT KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MASALASINING AHAMIYATI. RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR DAVRIDA TILLARNI INTENSIV O‘QITISHNING PSIXOLOGIK- PEDAGOGIK JIHATLARI RESPUBLIKA ILMIY-AMALIY ANJUMANI. 2023-yil 2-iyun (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7993607>)
2. Jalilova D.U. Psychological And Technological Features of Increasing the Efficiency of Educational Activity of Talented Students in Presidential Schools. Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices ISSN NO: 2770-2367 (<https://zienjournals.com>).
3. Mahfuza Tursunqulova To‘lqin qizi. ZAMONAVIY TA‘LIM SHAROITIDA O‘QUVCHILARIDA LINGVISTIK KOMPETENSIYALARNI SHAKLLANTIRISH MASALASI VA YONDASHUVNING AHAMIYATI UYG‘UNLIGI. “RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR DAVRIDA TILLARNI INTENSIV O‘QITISHNING PSIXOLOGIK-PEDAGOGIK JIHATLARI” MAVZUSIDAGI RESPUBLIKA ILMIY-AMALIY ANJUMANI. 01.06.2023 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7993657>.
4. Tursunqulova Maxfuza To‘lqin qizi. BOSHLANG‘ICH SINFLARDA FOYDALANILADIGAN DIDAKTIK O‘YINLAR HAQIDA AYRIM MULOHAZALAR. YANGILANAYOTGAN O‘ZBEKISTON TARAQQIYOTIDA IQTISODIY FANLARNI O‘QITISHNING DOLZARB MASALALARI ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya 2023.

- <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8044429/>
<http://scientists.uz/uploads/conferences/007/1.94.pdf>
5. Tursunqulova Maxfuza To‘lqin qizi. BOSHLANG‘ICH SINFLARDA FOYDALANILADIGAN DIDAKTIK O‘YINLAR HAQIDA AYRIM MULOHAZALAR. YANGILANAYOTGAN O‘ZBEKISTON TARAQQIYOTIDA IQTISODIY FANLARNI O‘QITISHNING DOLZARB MASALALARI. 15.06.2023
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8044429>
6. https://t.me/jalilova_dilshoda_2292
7. https://t.me/ilmiy_yordam_beraman